

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the background of the study, theoretical framework, conceptual framework, statement of the problem, hypothesis, objectives of the study, scope and limitations, paradigm of the study, and operational definition of terms.

Background of the study

The main aim of education is to modify the behavior of child according to the needs and expectation of the society (Balaji, 2017). Attitude of the learners has been viewed as the predisposition to respond positively or negatively toward an object or phenomena, thus, the learners' attitudes may affect their performances in school. However, Mallick (n.d.) stated that it is not possible for any teacher to develop scientific attitudes among the students unless the beliefs and notions of the students were eradicated. Therefore, one of the important duties of the teachers is to adopt scientific attitude in him\herself and to make use of various scientific methods for imparting information of various facts and concepts. In such kind of situation, students will try to follow the path which their teacher had shown them. Aside from, modern educational thought regards to the imparting of the scientific attitude as a fundamental obligation of science teaching (Wiley, 2019).

In addition, according to the study of Singh and Bai (2017), science learning provides training in scientific method and also helps to develop scientific attitudes. Moreover, attitude acts as directive factors when a child enters into a new experience. As a result, attitudes carry an emotion on an intellectual tone, both of which making decisions and forming evaluations. The decisions and evaluations can cause a child to set priorities and hold different preferences.

Loo National High School has two types of special program which are the Special Science Class and the Special Performing in the Arts. The Special Science Class has an advance subject which is Research and they tend to focus on academics especially on the field of Science, Math and Research. Further, they spend six hours of their subject in Math and Science every week. On the other hand, Special Performing in the Arts focuses on the field of Arts and Music. Particularly, it is sub-divided into dance drama, musical plays, instruments, and arts. Both special programs have creative writing which is an activity or work that is artistic, in which, it includes an idea that is not plain but rather, entertaining to read. Aside from, Special Science Class is from grades 7 to 10, however, Special Performing in the Arts is from grades 7 to 8 for it was implemented two years ago. Thus, both special programs don't have Technological and Livelihood Education subject.

Moreover, the study aims to know the scientific attitudes of Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners at Loo National High School. It will only focus to the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners of grade-7. In addition, this study is to determine if there are differences and similarities on the scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners when they are categorized into various group. In particular, it targets to identify the common scientific attitude and level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners when grouped according to sex and types of special programs. Lastly, to find out how the learners improve their scientific attitudes.

This study is beneficial to the students, learners' parents, school personnel, future researchers, and school. Generally, this helps them for improvement and better understanding. In particular, the study is beneficial to the students for them to enhance their scientific attitudes, which gives an idea to the school and school personnel in order to have

a better management and teaching skills. Further, it helps the parents to know their children's scientific attitudes and be able to guide them which is beneficial to learners' academic performance.

Theoretical Framework

Social Learning Theory

Social learning theory explains human behavior in terms of continuous reciprocal interaction between cognitive, behavioral, and environmental influences (Mobley and Sandoval, 2008). It is a way of learning through observing and modelling the behavior, attitudes, and reaction of other people. In particular, the use of Social learning theory in science teaching for the acquisition of scientific attitudes is, the teaching activities might increase the effectiveness of general education by taking the scientific and affective aspects into consideration in order to develop scientific attitude and planning (Demirbras and Yagbasan, 2016). Thus, developing scientific attitudes can be conducted by role playing. Using this method, the development of scientific attitude may be accomplished by focusing the students' learning to specific objectives through a series of persuasive communications oriented towards the cognitive domain of the individual attitude (Kereh et. al, 2017).

The research undertaking is anchored to Social Learning Theory for it deals with the developing of attitudes through imitating and observing other people. Besides, this can happen in school activities like role playing to enhance the scientific attitudes of the learners through communicating.

Western Philosophy

The study is anchored to Western Philosophy. Western Philosophy claims that the original meaning of skepticism is “an inquirer” (skeptikos) or someone who was unsatisfied and still looking for the truth. In everyday life, practically everyone is skeptical about some knowledge claims but philosophical skeptics have doubted the possibility of any knowledge beyond that of the content of directly experience (Popkin, 2019). The study is related to western philosophy for it is all about a certain scientific attitude which is skepticism. Additionally, the research undertaking focuses on identifying the scientific attitudes of the learners, in which, skepticism is one of its scope.

Philosophical View of Critical Thinking

Critical thinking is one of the most important aspects of philosophy. In fact, without critical thinking, there will be no scientific method. It has actually three categories introduced by philosophers as early as Socrates in the ancient Greek which are the deductive thinking, inductive thinking, and abductive thinking. Generally, these three categories are used to analyze one’s beliefs regarding morals as well. Deductive thinking allows a person to reach conclusions while inductive thinking allows a person to generalize the phenomena in much the way that science uses experimentation to test predictions and form scientific theories. Then, abductive thinking is described as “reasoning by analogy” and it is the one required when entering into a new field (Cooper, 2018). The research undertaking is correlated to the philosophical view of critical thinking for it discusses one of the scientific attitudes which the study is engaged with.

Conceptual Framework

Scientific Attitudes

Raja (2016) stated that scientific attitude enables us to think rationally for it is the combination of many qualities and virtues which is reflected through the behavior and action of the person. In addition, a philosopher of science argues that science is not characterized by a specific scientific method but by the scientific attitude, because scientists value empirical evidence and follow the evidence wherever it leads (Hall, 2019). A scientific attitude can be defined as way of viewing things and curiosity to know how and why things happen with an open-mind. Having a scientific attitude means accepting only facts that have been carefully verified, together with a willingness to discard old theories that new facts tend to displace (Palitayan, 2019).

Additionally, it is one of the eternal questioning, and eternal reliance on the evidence of experience (Howard, 2018). According to Pudlao (2012), scientific attitude is an important aspect of a personality of someone who wants to be successful in the field of science. According to the past study of Singh (n.d.), scientific attitude can be regarded as a complex of values and norms that are supposed to be internalized by someone, which is held to be binding on the man of science. Further, the study of Kaur (2013) states that scientific attitudes helps to tackle problem objectively without bias promoting logical thinking.

1. Curiosity. Curiosity is reckoned to be the soul of knowledge. In this instance, knowledge remains a bunch of facts, unlimited information, and useful skills acquired by a person through experience. This can go along with the practical understanding of a subject. In addition, curiosity is the inner and hidden power that urges people to know, stay

informed and to be aware of what is happening around them and beyond (Yazid, 2019). According to Sasson (2019), it widens the mind and opens it to different opinions, different lifestyles and different topics. Curiosity also leads to learning, acquiring knowledge, and becoming an expert in one's field. Curiosity is a vital ingredient for becoming a good journalist, writer, inventor or scientist. Aside from that, it is an important ingredient of the process of learning at every age. Curiosity awakens interest, motivation and a feeling of being alive. Curiosity is great, but it needs to be encouraged and fostered.

2. Open-mindedness. The ability to accept, respect and listen to new ideas and criticism of other people (Quizlet Inc., 2019). However, open-mindedness is the willingness to search actively for evidence against one's favored beliefs, plans, or goals, and to weigh such evidence fairly when it is available. Being open-minded is important because it opens up opportunities in able to learn from others, learn about the way they live, the way they believe and what they do. It allows you to become aware and live in a way that's more approachable (Gerard, 2017).

3. Skepticism. According to Tabinga (2014.), skepticism is not accepting things blindly without questioning. Additionally, skepticism is the willing suspension of belief, and requires to apply reason to all ideas that are presented. This attitude refers to both philosophical stance and an everyday attitude of doubting, but not necessarily denying the truth of commonly held beliefs. Having skeptical attitude is really important for doing ethics well (Pearson Education, 2019).

4. Intellectual Honesty. It is the way of always seeking the truth regardless of whether or not it agrees with your own personal beliefs. For a business, this means that decisions are grounded by facts, not by the stature or position of the individual within the

company presenting it (Entrepreneur Media, 2016). Further, intellectual honesty is the cornerstone of the development and acquisition of knowledge. In academic circles, intellectual honesty is deemed a prized item as this is what defines knowledge, the way it is generated and disseminated. It is open to all forms of critique by just about anyone interested in the subject. This is a safeguard against any devious agenda held by vested interest groups in promoting the so-called knowledge in the interest of many (Razak, 2019).

5. Creativity. Creativity pervades human life. It is the mark of individuality, the vehicle of self-expression and the engine of progress in every human endeavor. It also raises a wealth of philosophical questions but curiously, it hasn't been a major topic in contemporary philosophy (Paul and Kaufman, 2019). In addition, creativity is defined as the tendency to recognize or generate ideas, alternatives, or possibilities that may be useful in solving problems, communicating with others, and entertaining yourself with others (Franken, n.d.). Having this attitude expands ones' perceptions and along with expanded perceptions come new ways of solving problems (Roe, 2012).

6. Keen Observer. Mertz (2016) stated that keen observer is also called good observant, wherein, what people observed in the out-of-ordinary may produce a moment of wonder that they can apply. This means noticing things that other people missed and paying attention to both big picture and small details (Brand, 2018). Thus, being a keen observer matters for it creates better lessons for ones" to embrace and put into action. Besides, it translates the person into being an empathetic leader, who adapts and creates a legacy that others may remember (Navarro, 2012).

7. Risk-taking. Someone who risks loss or injury in the hope of gain (Palitayan, 2019). In addition, it is any consciously or non-consciously controlled behavior with a

perceived uncertainty about its outcome, and/or about its possible benefits or costs for the physical, economic or psycho-social well-being of oneself or others. The concept of risk described so far largely refers to insuring oneself against possible loss, and the most accurate calculation of the costs and benefits involved. In addition, uncertainty in risk taking behavior is not only in the probability of an outcome occurrence, but also in the perceived probability of its outcome value (Elsevier, 2020).

8. Objectivity. According to Pudlao (2012), it is the act of not allowing ones' feelings and biases to influence the result of something. Further, ideas that show objectivity are based on facts and are free from bias or personal opinion. In science, even hypotheses, or ideas about how something may work, are written in a way that are objective. This means that experiments may prove a hypothesis false if the data does not support it. Scientists will alter hypotheses and theories when new knowledge is developed. Objectivity is important in science because scientific studies seek to get as close to the truth as possible, not just prove a hypothesis (Steele, 2003).

9. Critical Thinking. Islam (2015) stated that it is the ability to analyze the way a person thinks and presents evidence from own ideas, rather than simply accepting own personal reasoning as sufficient proof. People can gain numerous benefits from mastering critical thinking skills, such as better control of own learning and empathy for other points of view. Critical thinking is, in short, self-directed, self-disciplined, self-monitored, and self-corrective thinking. It presupposes assent to rigorous standards of excellence and mindful command of their use. It entails effective communication and problem solving abilities and a commitment to overcome native egocentrism and sociocentrism. Aside from, critical thinking enhances language and presentation skills.

10. Persistence. Persistence is continuation of effort and striving in the face of difficulty, opposition, or failure: it is a key characteristic of successful people across professional and academic disciplines. It is evidenced by willingness to continue to try in the face of challenge. For students, this persistence can be a driving force to help them achieve their academic, as well as personal goals. The idea of persistence in the face of adversity is often described as an outcome of high motivation (Dana, n.d.). Persistence allows people to keep taking action even when they don't feel motivated to do so. In contrast, lack of persistence is one of the most common reasons for failure in any endeavor, for a little more persistence, a little more effort is sometimes what is needed to get closer to the goal (Oppong, 2017).

Special Programs

1. Special Science Class. It is implemented by Department of Education to pursue the Special Science Curriculum which is a special curriculum that is designed to and formulated to enrich the competencies of advanced and scientifically inclined learners. In order to ensure that all scholars or beneficiaries of the special science class, the Department of Science and Technology prescribes and provides the selection test for applicants who are willing to undergo rigid screening. To qualify as examinees, the students must reach a particular grade requirement in major subjects like English, Science, and Mathematics, and must cope with the required general average. Once qualified to be beneficiary of the Special Science Class, the learner is required to maintain a target grade not lower than 80 and must comply with an 85 required general average (Sun Star Baguio, 2017).

2. Special Performing in the Arts. It offers affordable adaptive singing, dancing, and acting classes. It aims to make the students learn to express themselves through creative

group music and movement activities while gaining confidence and appreciation for the arts. Further, Special Performing in the Arts offers personal attention to meet each students' specific needs. All classes culminate in a live performance for friends and family (Sun Star Baguio, 2017).

The paradigm of the study shows the relationship among the variables of this study. Box 1 contained the Demographic Profile that serves as the independent variable of the study which consists sex and types of special programs of Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners. Box 2 contained the dependent variable which is the topmost scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners and level of the scientific attitudes as to sex and types of special program that has a rating from high, to moderate, to low, and to poor. Lastly, box 2 contains how the learners improve their scientific attitudes as to sex and types of special program.

Figure 1. Paradigm of the Study

Statement of the Problem

The study aimed to determine the different scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs at Loo National High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the common scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program?
2. What is the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program?
3. How can the grade-7 learners improve their scientific attitudes under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program?

Hypothesis of the Study

The following hypothesis are to be proven upon the completion of the research:

1. The common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when they are grouped according to sex and types of special program is creativity.
2. The level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners when they are grouped according to sex and types of special program is moderate.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the different scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs at Loo National High School. Specifically, it sought to answer the following objectives:

1. Identify the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program.
2. Determine the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of program.
3. Find out how the grade-7 learners under the special programs improve their scientific attitude when they are grouped according to sex and types of special program.

Scope and Limitation

The research was conducted during the second semester of the school year from November 2019 until March 2020. The study was conducted at Loo National High School, Lanas, Loo, Bugias, Benguet. The chosen respondents were grade-7 learners under the special programs specifically the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts. The researchers conducted this study to identify the learners' common scientific attitude, determine the level of scientific attitudes, and find out how they improve their scientific attitudes when they are grouped according to sex and types of special program. Moreover, the study used descriptive design as a method of investigation. Observation, and survey questionnaire was used in gathering the data in a form of four-point likert scale and ranking.

Significance of the Study

Learners tend to develop and portray various scientific attitudes inside the school premises, wherein, it was mostly shown during their performances and behavior during class. Besides, it influences the way they absorb and react to any aspects of learning that they experience. In line with, this study can help the following:

a) Students. This study is significant to the students for them to enhance their scientific attitudes in school especially that it has effects on their academic performances. Additionally, the students may be able to use it in class for a better learning.

b) School Teacher. It helps them have a knowledge and idea about their students' scientific attitudes, thus, for them to amend and improve their strategies in teaching. Further, this study is significant to the school personnel for them to have a better understanding on the scientific attitudes of the learners in their class.

c) Learners' Parents. This helps them know and be informed about their children's scientific attitudes and be able to guide them. Additionally, parents guiding their own children basing on their scientific attitudes can lead to a better performance.

d) Future Researchers. The research undertaking will help them generate new ideas and for them to have a basis in conducting similar research. This will serve as a guide for them to improve their research and have a better output that is significant to the school and community.

e) School. It helps the school to be informed regarding the scientific attitudes of the learners. Thus, the school can implement necessary activities that can increase the level of scientific attitudes of the learners to become more productive inside and outside the school campus.

Operational Definition of Terms

SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDE – personality of someone who wants to learn more and enhance their understanding about something.

CURIOSITY – a desire to learn and to know more about something.

SKEPTICISM – seeking for a reliable information.

OPEN-MINDEDNESS – considering the ideas and opinions of other people.

INTELLECTUAL HONESTY – the quality of being truthful in stating insights and beliefs.

CREATIVITY – the ability to discover and make new things, and to think of new ideas.

KEEN OBSERVER – noticing thoroughly the things that people ignore or have overlooked.

RISK-TAKING – trying to do something even if there's a possibility of losing something.

OBJECTIVITY – learning from a reliable statement that doesn't involve personal beliefs.

CRITICAL THINKING – interpreting things with an in-depth understanding.

PERSISTENCE – exerting an effort to achieve a goal.

TYPES OF SPECIAL PROGRAM – it's either Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts.

SPECIAL PERFORMING IN THE ARTS - students that focuses in the field of music, visual, and dance drama.

SPECIAL SCIENCE CLASS – students who passed the entrance examination and have an average grade of 85 and above, in which, they are focused on Mathematics and Science.

SEX – being a male or female.

IMPROVEMENT – making something better than the previous one.

LEVEL OF SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDE – used to measure the level of scientific attitudes of Special Performing in the Arts and Special Science Class learners based on their participation at school, it could be high, moderate, low, and poor.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The study is anchored to Cognitive Consistency Theory. According to Sharma (n.d.), research has generally concluded that people seek consistency among their attitudes and their behavior. This means that people seek to reconcile divergent attitudes and align it to their behavior so that they appear rational and consistent. Attitudes are simply expressions of how much we like or dislike various things. Attitudes represent our evaluations, preferences or rejections based on the information we receive. Attitude may be defined as ‘an enduring predisposition or readiness to react or behave in a particular manner to a given object or situation, idea, material or person’. Further, it is a generalized tendency to think or act in a certain way in respect of some object or situation, often accompanied by feeling.

The research undertaking is connected to cognitive consistency theory for it involves the attitudes and behavior of every individual. In general, they are closely related for they both deal with various attitudes. However, the theory focuses only in attitudes particularly in the consistency and inconsistency of ones’ attitudes, although, the study concentrates in attitudes but it mainly focuses on scientific attitudes of learners under the special programs.

In addition, Sharma stated that planning learning experiences to inculcate scientific attitudes, some experts have put forwarded their views. In accordance with an expert’s view, this can be done by increasing the degree of consistency of the environment in which students get education. For this, number of opportunities for making satisfying adjustments to attitude situations should be increased and this can only be done by providing more opportunities to the students for analysis of problem or different kinds of situations as a

result of which they can understand them properly and can bring about intellectual and desirable kind of changes in their attitude.

In simple terms, the measures through which scientific attitudes can be developed among the students include those through which their curiosity gets satisfied, they get rid of their superstitions, they begin to participate in co-curricular activities, they begin to think in a practical way, they play an important role in developing a desirable kind of environment in the classroom, they get inspired to get involved in the habit of studying various scientific literatures and they get opportunities to get involved in practicing or practical works (Mallick, n.d.). Aside from, as stated by Khan et. al (2012) in their study that the assessment of scientific attitude (affective domain) is not as simple as compared to that of the scientific knowledge (cognitive domain) and science process skills (Psych motive domain) and this scientific attitude is one of the important aspects of today's science throughout the globe. Scientific attitude is an attitude which will tend to foster scientific achievement. The scientific attitude is closely related to scientific method, for the attitude gives rise to the method, and the method gives evidence to the attitude (Wiley, 2019).

Science, in the curriculum, provides certain scientific values which are not provided by any other subject. The school subjects are taught because they provide liberal education; they are part of the equipment and preparation for life which was expected to schools to give it to students so that they may play their part in the community as intellectual citizens. Science is extremely important to one's education just like any subjects offered in school. Additionally, it provides information and understanding to principles within the facets of living and non-living matters. Supplementary to this, learning science provides the practice of scientific method which develops the scientific attitude, which leads the person to think

critically and value facts with evidence. Scientific attitude plays a major role in science education and in the lives of students pursuing science education. This growing awareness of the need and importance of science has become mostly manifested in the Philippines (Lacap, 2015).

The Philippine Education System, in its thrust of being globally competitive, continuously upgrades its' various program and curricular (Sebastian, 2012). In line with, special education programs work to help individuals develop not only their academic skills, but also the personal skills that help them become self-sufficient members of the community. Aside from, special programs and services adapt content and teaching methodology and deliver instruction to meet the needs of each student (Anon, 2019). Anthony (2020), Special Interest Program of DepEd includes Special Program in the Arts and Special Science Program.

In 2000, the Department of Education launched in the Special Program in the Arts. This nationwide program aims to foster the potentials of artistically-inclined students. Public high schools that offer this program are selected based on the criteria established by the Department of Education. The Special Program in the Arts implements a secondary education curriculum with an additional subject that is centered in the arts. There are five fields in the SPA: Creative Writing (English and Filipino), Visual Arts, Theater Arts, Vocal Music, Instrumental Music, Dance and Media Arts (Leocario and Pawilen, 2015).

Based on the K to 12 science curriculum, science education aims to develop scientific literacy among students that will prepare them to be informed and participative citizens who are able to make judgments and decisions regarding applications of scientific knowledge that may have social, health or environmental impacts. It is designed around

the three domains of learning science: understanding and applying scientific knowledge, performing scientific process skills, then developing and demonstrating scientific attitudes and values. Maranan (2012) states that in Science Curriculum Guide, the K to 12 Curriculum is constructed around the three basic dimensions of the nature of science. The first of these is the science content of scientific knowledge. The other two important dimensions are science process skills, scientific attitudes and values. All these could be applied in own locality as well as globally.

Additionally, Panoy (2013) cited that the goal of science education is to develop students' skills and enables individuals to apply those skills in everyday lives. These skills affect the personal, social, and global life of individuals. Besides, scientific attitudes are the most important outcomes of science teaching. Thus, science should be taught directly and systematically because developing scientific attitudes has a number of characteristics which distinguishes it from other attitudes (Gokul and Malliga, 2015).

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the research design, population and locale of the study, research instruments, data gathering procedure, and treatment of data.

Research Design

The researchers used descriptive research design as a method of investigation in this study. As stated by Bhat (2019), descriptive research design is a method that describes the characteristics of population or phenomenon that is being studied. Aside from, it is a qualitative and quantitative method to investigate one or more variables (McCombes, 2019).

The study opted to describe the difference of the common scientific attitude and level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs, including on how they improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex and types of special program. Further, the researchers applied descriptive research design for the reason that qualitative and quantitative method were used in this study. The quantitative method was to identify the common and level of scientific attitudes of the grade-7 learners as to sex and special types of program. However, qualitative method is to find out how the learners improve their scientific attitudes as to sex and types of program.

Population and Locale of the Study

The research undertaking was conducted at Loo National High School, Lanas, Loo, Buguias, Benguet. In particular, the study focused on grade-7 learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts. Moreover, the chosen respondents were

28 Special Science Class learners and 70 Special Performing in the Arts learners to identify the learners' common scientific attitude, level of scientific attitudes, and how they improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex and types of special program. Overall, the researchers utilized 98 grade-7 learners under the special program.

Research Instruments

The researchers used survey questionnaire with the used of table form questions and open-ended questions to gather the needed data. Additionally, the questionnaire used four-point scaled questions specifically in the table form questions. Survey questionnaires were conceptualized with the help of the research teacher, and gathering of data were personally conducted by the researchers. Further, it is subjected to reliability using Cronbach's Alpha.

The survey questionnaire was divided into three parts. Part I consists the demographic profile of the learners which is the name, sex, and types of special program. Then, part II contained the table form questions that used four-point scaled questions to answer problem 1 and 2 regarding the common scientific attitude and the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs as to sex and types of special program. Lastly, part III was composed of an open-ended question to answer problem 3 which is how can grade-7 learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts improve their scientific attitudes.

Data Gathering Procedure

First, communication letter was sent to the school principal at Loo National High School by the researchers to ask for her approval and permission regarding this study. Further, after the questionnaire was subjected to reliability using Cronbach's Alpha, data gathering followed. Additionally, the researchers asked the teacher in-charge for the class of Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners for his/her permission for the distribution of the survey questionnaires. In addition, a letter of consent was attached to each of the survey questionnaires. Then after the gathering of data, organization, and tabulation of data were next.

Treatment of Data

The researchers tallied, categorized, and analyzed the gathered data basing on the statement of the problem in this study. Generally, descriptive statistics were used for data analysis which was summarized and simplified through tabulation.

In particular, to answer problem 1 which is the common scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program, mean and ranking were used.

Then, to answer problem 2 regarding on the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special programs, the following scale of interpretation were used:

Relative Value	Statistical Limit	Level	Description
4	3.26-4.00	High (H)	100%
3	2.51-3.25	Moderate (Mo)	75%
2	1.76-2.50	Low (L)	50%
1	1.00-1.75	Poor (P)	25%

Lastly, to answer problem 3 which is how can grade-7 learners under the special programs improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex and types of special program, summarization, coding, and transcribing were used.

RESULTS AND DISSCUSION

This chapter presents the findings of the study based from the collected data using a survey questionnaire. It was presented in tables and arranged as to the order of the objectives of the study.

Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex

Generally, the first objective of the study is to determine the common scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the Special Performing in the Arts and Special Science Class. In particular, it focuses on identifying the learners' common scientific attitude when grouped according to sex such as female and male.

The findings present that persistence has the highest computed mean which is 3.35 for female; then 2.99 for persistence and creativity for grade-7 male learners. Aside from, the following were the sequence of the female learners' scientific attitudes from highest to lowest mean; keen observer, curiosity, intellectual honesty, risk-taking, open-mindedness, objectivity, skepticism, creativity, and critical thinking with a total mean of 3.26, 3.07, 3.05, 2.96, 2.9, 2.8, 2.77, 2.72, and 2.5 respectively. On the other hand, the ranking of the scientific attitudes of male learners are risk-taking, keen observer, objectivity, curiosity, skepticism, open-mindedness, critical thinking, and intellectual honesty with computed means of 2.82, 2.81, 2.75, 2.72, 2.68, 2.55, 2.35, and 2.21.

Mean computation and ranking were used to determine the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex.

Table 1.a. Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex

Scientific Attitudes	Female (mean)	Rank	Male (mean)	Rank
Curiosity	3.07	3	2.72	6
Open-Mindedness	2.9	6	2.55	8
Skepticism	2.77	8	2.68	7
Intellectual Honesty	3.05	4	2.21	10
Creativity	2.72	9	2.99	1
Keen Observer	3.26	2	2.81	4
Risk-Taking	2.96	5	2.82	3
Objectivity	2.8	7	2.75	5
Critical Thinking	2.5	10	2.35	9
Persistence	3.35	1	2.99	1

The computed means were the basis in ranking the scientific attitudes of male and female learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts. Further, the scientific attitudes were ranked from highest to lowest mean. In connection, basing from the results of the computed data, hypothesis number one stating that the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs is creativity when grouped according to sex is rejected.

Thus, the interpreted data denotes that the common scientific attitude of female and male learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts is persistence. It denotes that the learners exert efforts in doing their requirements such as approaching their teacher to clear the instruction regarding the activity that was given to them. Aside from, the learners tend to asked the teacher about the lessons that they didn't understand on the book that they had read. On the other hand, it turned out that creativity is another common scientific attitude of male grade-7 learners. This shows that the learners used their talents and skills to produce a creative work. It indicates that male learners inside the school campus performed well using their skills and talents during presentation in their

subjects such as participating well in the culminating activity that includes dancing and role playing.

This study opposes the findings of Lacap (2015) regarding the common scientific attitude of the science major students at Pangasinan State University, Bayambang Campus for it was stated that open-mindedness is the common scientific attitude of science major students. Thus, both studies had different results for Lacap explained that open-mindedness ranked first for most of the science major students respect and listen to the ideas of others, accept criticism, and changes their mind in the face of reliable evidence contrary to what they believe in. However, persistence and creativity ranked first in this study for it shows that most of the grade-7 learners don't easily give up on the things that they are doing even though it has difficulty, and the learners perform inside the school premises using their talents and skills to produce a creative work and new ideas.

Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of special program

The first objective of the research undertaking is to identify the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners when grouped according to types of special program. Specifically, the study mainly highlights the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners.

Basing from the findings of the study, persistence with 3.39 mean is the common scientific attitude of Special Science Class category while creativity for Special Performing in the Arts for having a mean of 3.12, then critical thinking situated as their last place with a total mean of 2.59 and 2.4. Further, keen observer ranked second under the both special

Table 1.b. Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of special program

Scientific attitudes	Special Science Class (Mean)	Rank	Special Performing in the Arts (Mean)	Rank
Curiosity	3.06	5	3.05	3
Open-mindedness	2.99	7	2.75	7
Skepticism	2.86	9	2.69	8
Intellectual Honesty	3.07	4	2.86	5
Creativity	3.23	3	3.12	1
Keen observer	3.25	2	3.09	2
Risk Taking	3.05	6	2.91	4
Objectivity	2.99	7	2.73	6
Critical Thinking	2.59	10	2.4	10
Persistence	3.39	1	2.66	9

programs with a mean of 3.25 and 3.09. Then, Special Science Class has a total mean of 3.23 in terms of creativity, then 3.07 by intellectual honesty, 3.06 by curiosity, then risk-taking with 3.05 mean, open-mindedness and objectivity with 2.99, then skepticism that has 2.86 mean which ranked ninth. Additionally, for Special Performing in the Arts category, the ranking of the learners' scientific attitudes with their mean are 3.05, 2.91, 2.86, 2.73, 2.75, 2.69, and 2.66 in terms of curiosity, risk-taking, intellectual honesty, objectivity, open-mindedness, skepticism, and critical thinking.

In connection, to identify the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of special program, mean computation and ranking were used. The computed mean of each indicator were served as the basis in ranking the scientific attitudes of Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners. In particular, the ranking starts with the highest to the lowest computed mean to identify the common scientific attitude of the two categories. Moreover, basing

from the results, hypothesis number one which conveys that the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners is creativity when grouped according to types of program is rejected.

Reject the hypothesis for the findings presents that for the Special Science Class learners, their common scientific attitude is persistence, although, it ranked as ninth in the Special Performing in the Arts category. Thus, it only reveals that Special Science Class learners persist to do the activities that was given to them. For instance, the learners tend to answer the open-ended question that was given to them using English language despite of having grammatical errors. Further, creativity as the common scientific attitude of Special Performing in the Arts learners denotes how they frequently used arts and creative strategies such as song, broadcasting, reporting and others in their presentations. Moreover, the learners always show how active they are in the field of arts like performing flute and guitar during school programs.

Besides, the findings is connected to the study of Pitafi and Farooq (2012) entitled “Measurement of Scientific Attitude of Secondary School Students in Pakistan” in which, curiosity ranked first for having the highest computed mean. The study opposes the findings of Pitafi and Farooq for the results showed that persistence ranked first in the Special Science Class category and creativity for Special Performing in the Arts learners. Both studies had different findings for Pitafi and Farooq stated that interest of the students should be created in science teaching by making them curious and discovery approach should replace the conventional methods in science teaching. On the other hand, persistence and creativity ranked first for the learners give their best in doing the school activities, participate well in conducting presentation during the events at school, and using artistic materials to have a new creative work.

Table 2.a. Level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex

Scientific attitudes	Female (Mean)	Descriptive Equivalence	Male (Mean)	Descriptive Equivalence
Curiosity	3.07	Moderate	2.72	Moderate
Open-mindedness	2.9	Moderate	2.55	Moderate
Skepticism	2.77	Moderate	2.68	Moderate
Intellectual Honesty	3.05	Moderate	2.21	Moderate
Creativity	2.72	Moderate	2.99	Moderate
Keen observer	3.26	High	2.81	Moderate
Risk Taking	2.96	Moderate	2.82	Moderate
Objectivity	2.8	Moderate	2.75	Moderate
Critical Thinking	2.5	Moderate	2.35	Moderate
Persistence	3.35	High	2.99	Moderate
Average	2.94	Moderate	2.69	Moderate

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (High)

2.51-3.25 (Moderate)

1.76-2.50 (Low)

1.00-1.75 (Poor)

The second objective of the study is to determine the level of scientific attitudes of the grade-7 learners under the special programs. Thus, they are grouped according to sex such as female and male.

Generally, table 2.a. shows the overall average mean of male and female learners which are 2.94 and 2.69 that means their level of scientific attitudes is moderate. In particular, female learners had a high level of scientific attitudes in terms of being a keen observer and having persistence with a total mean of 3.26 and 3.35. Overall, the learners' scientific attitudes had a descriptive equivalence of moderate in terms of curiosity, open-mindedness, skepticism, intellectual honesty, creativity, keen observer, risk-taking, objectivity, critical thinking and persistence with a mean ranging from 2.51-3.25.

Mean computation was used to determine the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex. In addition, table 2.a

used a legend in identifying the descriptive equivalence of the computed mean of each scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs. Hypothesis 2 which states that the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs is moderate when grouped according to sex is accepted.

Accept the hypothesis for the average mean of female and male category has a descriptive equivalence of moderate. This implies that both learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts has generally moderate level of scientific attitudes. It indicates that the learners were not having too much difficulty in applying the scientific attitudes especially at school which helps them in any aspects of learning. Additionally, it helps them understand the lessons more by trying to analyze the details before asking the teacher. Thus, having a moderate level of scientific attitudes by the female and male learners shows how they act and behave at school, particularly, participating confidently in any activities or programs inside the school campus such as Buwan ng Wika, and showing talents during school competitions.

Therefore, the findings of the study is connected to the study of Ataha et.al. (2013) entitled “An investigation of the Scientific Attitude among science students in the senior secondary schools in Edo South Senatorial District, Edo State”. It revealed that the level of scientific attitudes among the science students is average, in which the research undertaking has the same result which denotes that this study is in agreement with the findings of Ataha et.al. It also stated in the study that the scientific attitude can be improved by organizing a purposeful activity such as science fair, quizzes, debates, and science exhibition. Modern scientific magazines, journals and films should be provided in school for students to use. Additionally, Meera (2017) stated in his study entitled “An

Investigation of Scientific Attitude among Secondary School students in Kottayam District of Kerala” that the scientific attitudes of secondary students had a level of moderate. Meera concluded that there is a need for humanizing science to develop proper appreciation towards science. Aside from, it was also recommended in the study that teachers can inculcate scientific attitude in their student by scientific discussions, conducting experiment, and giving training.

Level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of program

The second objective of the study is to determine the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners. Specifically, it focuses on the special program which are Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners.

Basing from the results, it presents that Special Science Class has an average mean of 3.04 while 2.83 for Special Performing in the Arts which implies that the learners has a moderate level of scientific attitudes. Moreover, persistence has a mean of 3.39 which has descriptive equivalence of high under the Special Science Class. The mean ranging from 2.51-3.25 has a descriptive equivalence of moderate which are curiosity, open-mindedness, skepticism, intellectual honesty, creativity, keen observer, risk taking, objectivity, critical thinking, and persistence.

Further, to determine the level of scientific attitudes of grade -7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of special program, mean computation was utilized. Then, legend was used to distinguish the descriptive equivalence of the computed mean of the data if it is High (3.26-4.00), Moderate (2.51-3.25), Low (1.76-

Table 2.b. Level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of program

Scientific Attitudes	Special Science Class (Mean)	Descriptive Equivalence	Special Performing in the Arts (Mean)	Descriptive Equivalence
Curiosity	3.06	Moderate	3.05	Moderate
Open-mindedness	2.99	Moderate	2.75	Moderate
Skepticism	2.86	Moderate	2.69	Moderate
Intellectual Honesty	3.07	Moderate	2.86	Moderate
Creativity	3.23	Moderate	3.12	Moderate
Keen Observer	3.25	Moderate	3.09	Moderate
Risk Taking	3.05	Moderate	2.91	Moderate
Objectivity	2.99	Moderate	2.73	Moderate
Critical Thinking	2.59	Moderate	2.4	Moderate
Persistence	3.39	High	2.66	Moderate
Average	3.05	Moderate	2.83	Moderate

Legend: 3.26-4.00 (High)

2.51-3.25 (Moderate)

1.76-2.50 (Low)

1.00-1.75 (Poor)

2.50), and Poor (1.00-1.75). In line with, hypothesis number two conveys that the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs is moderate when grouped according to types special program is accepted.

Thus, the findings of the study implied that in general, grade-7 learners under the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts has a moderate level of scientific attitudes. This denotes that the learners under the special programs apply their scientific attitudes oftentimes, in which, it makes the learners widen their knowledge easily by in-depth understanding regarding the discussions and not relying on the teachers' explanation. It also means that the learners enhanced their skills and talents through observing and learning from the surroundings, and also accepting suggestions from fellow students or teachers.

The findings of the study is similar to the study of Pitafi and Farooq (2012) which is entitled as “Measurement of Scientific Attitude of Secondary School Students in Pakistan”. Their study stated that the level of the scientific attitude of secondary school student was moderate. Additionally, it also stated that the attitude to be taught must be identified and planned. Besides, Pitati and Farooq recommended that the students should be free to attempt their own patterns of exportation. Learning experiences must be selected on the basis of knowledge, skills and attitudes to be learned.

How the grade-7 learners under the special programs improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex

The third objective is to find out how the grade-7 learners under the special programs improve their scientific attitudes. Thus, it is grouped according to sex such as female and male.

The findings revealed that female and male learners improve their scientific attitudes through collaboration, conducting good manners, and exerting effort at school. Specifically, collaboration under the female category includes listening during class, participating in activities, passing requirements, and sharing ideas. Under good manners are self-discipline, careful judgement, honesty, and acceptance of others’ ideas while exerting effort at school includes reading, searching lessons, observing, never giving up, understanding the lessons, studying, and asking the teacher regarding the lessons that didn’t understand. Male learners had the same responses but the difference are under the part of exerting more effort, it includes taking notes and spending allowance for school requirements.

Therefore, the findings can be attributed to the fact that female and male learners under the Special Science Class has similar ways with regards on how they improve their scientific attitudes through collaboration, conducting good manners, and exerting more effort at school. Collaboration implies that the learners can improve their scientific attitudes by actively doing their best in the activities inside the school campus with unity. Thus, it increases the level of critical thinking, persistence and objectivity. Another are passing all the requirements before the deadline to avoid failing grades which can also enhance their time management, and sharing their ideas during class which increases the communication skills and intellectual honesty. Aside from, conducting good manners means that the grade-7 learners must have self-discipline, respect others especially teachers, wherein, the learners must learn to accept their fellow students' ideas, and they must not just give some pieces of advice but also accept so that they can develop open-mindedness. Then, exerting efforts at school implies that the learners must put some efforts in all the things that they are doing during class weather projects, activities, seat works and competitions for it can improve particularly, creativity and risk-taking. Further, the learners must not rely on the upcoming discussion, in which, they must have an advanced reading or search the possible lessons that they can tackle instead of waiting for the teacher to discuss, and they must ask the teacher regarding the lessons that they can't understand. This way, the learners can increase their level of scientific attitudes specifically, skepticism and curiosity. They must also take down notes in all the topics that have been discussed to improve their scientific attitudes in terms of keen observer.

In connection, a study of Kereh et. al (2017) represents a condition of the students at grade-7 in a middle school in Ambon. It stated that the scientific attitudes of the students

can improve using the scientific approach. This is in line with the note of psychological study, that learning can change the behavior as a result of an interaction with the environment that meeting the needs of the students. Additionally, students studying can develop and improve scientific attitudes by observing and a clear understanding of concepts. Regular practice and little intelligence can attain the scientific attitudes and hence, the academic achieve attainment (Raja, 2016).

How the grade-7 learners under the special programs improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to types of program

The third objective of the study is to find out how the grade-7 learners improve their scientific attitudes. It focuses on the learners under the special programs which are the Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts.

The results indicated that Special Science Class and Special Performing in the Arts learners improve their scientific attitudes by collaboration, exerting efforts at school and conducting good manners. Specifically, collaboration under the Special Science Class includes listening to the teacher, while exerting efforts adds-up reading, never giving up searching the lessons, observing, and understanding the lessons. Additionally, in conducting good manners, it includes accepting others' ideas and advices, and helping. On the other hand, the responses of the learners are similar, however, aside from the mentioned ways of improving scientific attitudes, Special Performing in the Arts category under the collaboration includes doing all the requirements and sharing ideas. Then under exerting efforts are asking the teacher regarding the lessons that can't be understand, taking notes, and spending allowance for projects. Lastly, under conducting good manners, it includes giving pieces of advice, respecting, honesty, and judging carefully.

Collaboration implies that the learners must behave and focus on the discussion to understand and analyze the lessons, quizzes, and projects that was given to them by the teacher, wherein, it can improve their critical thinking and persistence. Besides, collaboration inside the class can improve scientific attitudes for the learners won't just help their fellow classmates relate by stating their ideas and insights regarding their topic, rather, the learners can develop their intellectual honesty for they tend to show their thoughts and views which portrays honesty. Further, conducting good manners portrays that the learners must know how to consider others' opinions and learn from it even though it opposes ones' ideas, they must also respect others by accepting advices to strengthen goals and interpret it if it has a good or bad effects, and trying to give advices that can inspire fellow students which can help them realize something. Aside from, learners must evaluate carefully the works of fellow classmates to avoid disappointments. This develops open-mindedness and objectivity. Moreover, exerting effort means that the grade-7 learners under the special programs must help themselves by studying and analyzing deeply the ideas that they didn't understand by observing thoroughly the environment, and the learners must have an interest on the lessons that they are learning or about to learn, in which, they can ask their teacher if what is their next topic. Thus, this can improve curiosity and being a keen observer. The learners must also help their classmates by tutoring them if it is necessary and the learners must know how to sacrifice their allowance in making their projects and requirements at school that can improve risk-taking.

According to Balaji (2017), it was found that teachers' support with scientific temper can successfully develop scientific attitude in secondary school students. Thus, it can be concluded that the science teacher has an importune role to play in molding the

child's scientific attitude, a teacher. Teacher should train the students to transfer their learning to daily life situations and should relate science to other disciplines. Aside from, students should be given more exposure to activities that would enhance the development and improvement of scientific attitudes. The level of scientific attitudes be increased to improve academic performance.

FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter presents the findings and conclusions that were drawn from the study. Recommendations of the researchers were also included regarding the scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs.

Findings

The following statements were based on the results and discussion of the study:

1. The findings of the study stated that the common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs according to sex was persistence for female, then persistence and creativity for male. Aside from, when grouped according to types of special program, persistence for Special Science Class and creativity for Special Performing in the Arts learners.
2. The results of the study showed that the level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program was moderate.
3. The findings presented that grade-7 learners under the special programs can improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex and types of special programs through collaboration, exerting effort at school, and conducting good manners.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the conducted study, the researchers drew the following conclusions:

1. The common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special program was persistence for female and Special Science Class, while creativity and persistence for male, then creativity for Special Performing in the Arts. This indicated that female, male, and Special Science Class learners comply and participate with perseverance in their school requirements and activities. Additionally, most of the learners were responsible in doing all the tasks that were given to them by their teachers. Further, creativity which was another common scientific attitude of male and Special Performing in the Arts learners implied how they think and carry out things to come up with an interesting and creative output that nobody had done yet.

2. The level of scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex and types of special programs was moderate which means that the learners are not having too much hard time in their academic performances especially to the subjects they are hooked with. However, they must still improve their scientific attitudes to have a better learning and understanding.

3. The results indicated that grade-7 learners under the special programs can improve their scientific attitudes when grouped according to sex and types of special program through collaboration, exerting effort at school, and conducting good manners more than usual. This can improve the level of their skills, talents, and way of thinking which stimulates and enhances their scientific attitudes, this way, they will be more aware of their surroundings.

Recommendations

Based from this conclusions, the researchers therefore recommend the following:

1. The learners must not only concentrate on the common scientific attitude that they have, rather, they must also develop and improve the other scientific attitudes that they possess to enhance their talents and abilities.
2. The teachers must accommodate further the learners and give more activities such as experiments, researches, and creative reporting; the school can also implement more programs, competitions, and clubs that can increase the learners' level of scientific attitudes.
3. The learners must actively participate and observe in all the events happening inside the school premises to improve their scientific attitudes such as culminating activity, celebrations, and others.
4. Future researchers could conduct more studies regarding the scientific attitudes of grade-7 learners under the special programs.

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APPENDIX A

Letters

Republic of the Philippines
DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
Cordillera Administrative Region
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF BENGUET
LOO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Lanas, Loo, Buguias, Benguet

January 15, 2020

BIVIAN B. CUH-ING
School Principal I
Loo National High School
Lanas, Loo, Buguias, Benguet

Ma'am,

Greetings!

The Grade-12 STEM strand students are conducting a study entitled "SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDES OF GRADE-7 LEARNERS UNDER THE SPECIAL PROGRAMS" as one of the requirements in Inquiry, Investigation, and Immersion.

Thus, your permission is earnestly requested to allow the researchers administer the questionnaires to grade-7 students under the special programs. Rest assured that the collected data will be treated with utmost confidentiality and for educational purposes only.

Thank you very much for your approval.

Very Truly Yours,

MIKESON DANGPA
Researcher

WENZER CODMAN
Researcher

BRANDEL BAY-AN
Researcher

DOMINIJOYZ CULOP
Researcher

Noted:

JUVY DALE F. POLITCHAY
Research Teacher

Approved:

BIVIAN B. CUH-ING
School Principal

Republic of the Philippines
DEPARTMENT OF EDUCATION
Cordillera Administrative Region
SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF BENGUET
LOO NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL
Lanas, Loo, Buguias, Benguet

January 15, 2020

Dear Respondents,

Greetings!

The researchers are conducting a mixed method research as one of the requirements in Inquiry, Investigation, and Immersion. Thus, the study is entitled “SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDES OF GRADE-7 LEARNERS UNDER THE SPECIAL PROGRAMS”.

In relation to this, it is earnestly requested to please answer honestly and completely the attached survey questionnaire. Rest assured that your responses will be treated with utmost confidentiality and to be used for educational purposes only.

Thank you very much for your cooperation.

Very Truly Yours,

MIKESON DANGPA
Researcher

WENZER CODMAN
Researcher

BRANDEL BAY-AN
Researcher

DOMINIJOYZ CULOP
Researcher

Noted:

JUVY DALE F. POLITCHAY
Research Teacher

APPENDIX B

Survey Questionnaire

Direction: Dear respondents, please respond and provide the information asked to each item in the questionnaire honestly by checking (/).

PART I: DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

Name: _____ (Optional)

Sex: Male Female

Types of Special Program: Special Science Class
 Special Performing in the Arts

PART II: SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDES

The following are the different scientific attitudes, please check honestly according to your perception. Four-point likert scale below will help you determine your exact stand.

H- High (100) Mo- Moderate (75%) L- Low (50%) P- Poor (25%)

SCIENTIFIC ATTITUDES	H	Mo	L	P
Curiosity				
1) I always wanted to know our next lesson after the discussion.				
2) The class is more interesting when the teacher discusses new lessons.				
3) I always ask our teacher regarding the lessons for more information.				
Open-Mindedness				
1) I listen to the beliefs of others and tend to learn from it.				
2) I accept others' ideas, but still confirm it if it's correct or not.				
3) I don't mind if our topic in Biology is about reproductive system.				
Skepticism				
1) I ask our teacher regarding the things that I want to know during class.				
2) I do research about our topic for more understanding.				
3) I ask for tutor if I can't understand the lessons.				
Intellectual Honesty				
1) I answer the questions that I receive basing on my perceptions.				
2) I honestly state my ideas and opinions during class.				
3) I acknowledge all the sources and authors in my research.				
Creativity				
1) I can come up with an original design for my projects.				
2) Every project that I make has arts.				

3) I use my imagination to produce an artistic work.				
Keen Observer				
1) I pay attention closely in our activities.				
2) I comply and listen carefully during discussions.				
3) I perform at school basing on the standards of the teachers that I've noticed.				
Risk Taking				
1) I cooperate in sports during intramurals even though I/we might lose.				
2) I don't mind spending my allowance for my project.				
3) I sacrifice my sleep to study during exam.				
Objectivity				
1) I don't believe on ideas that I read without a valid evidence.				
2) I make sure to have a reliable source in my research.				
3) I don't rely on the internet in making my assignment.				
Critical Thinking				
1) I carefully judge others' work.				
2) I don't criticize others' belief.				
3) I secretly critic someone's claim and tend to learn from it.				
Persistence				
1) I push through something even though it's difficult.				
2) I do my best to pass all the requirements in my subjects.				
3) I don't give up on learning the lessons that I didn't understand.				

PART III:

Please answer honestly the following question according to your perception.
You can state your answer in a form of phrases/sentences/paragraph.

1. How can you improve your scientific attitude/s as a student? (You can state your answer as long as you can)

APPENDIX C

Raw Data

Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to sex

	H-High	Mo- Moderate	L-Low	P-Poor						
	FEMALE (n=71)					MALE (n=27)				
Scientific Attitudes	H (4)	Mo (3)	L (2)	P (1)	Mean	H (4)	Mo (3)	L (2)	P (1)	Mean
Curiosity										
1	24 (96)	40 (120)	7 (14)		3.24	2 (8)	18 (54)	6 (12)	1 (1)	2.78
2	22 (88)	44 (132)	5 (10)		3.24	5 (20)	16 (48)	5 (10)	1 (1)	2.93
3	8 (32)	39 (117)	20 (60)	4 (4)	2.72	2 (8)	14 (42)	5 (10)	6 (6)	2.44
Total					3.07					2.72
Open-mindedness										
1	19 (76)	43 (129)	7 (19)	1 (1)	3.10	4 (16)	12 (36)	10 (20)	1 (1)	2.70
2	29 (116)	32 (96)	9 (18)	1 (1)	3.25	1 (4)	16 (48)	9 (18)	1 (1)	2.63
3	10 (40)	24 (72)	18 (36)	19 (19)	2.35	5 (20)	5 (15)	11 (22)	6 (6)	2.33
Total					2.9					2.55
Skepticism										
1	22 (88)	31 (93)	11 (22)	7 (7)	2.96	4 (16)	14 (42)	6 (12)	3 (3)	2.70
2	20 (80)	33 (99)	14 (28)	4 (4)	2.97	4 (16)	11 (33)	8 (16)	4 (4)	2.56
3	4 (16)	31 (93)	23 (46)	13 (13)	2.37	7 (28)	8 (24)	11 (22)	1 (1)	2.78
Total					2.77					2.68
Intellectual Honesty										
1	32 (128)	32 (96)	7 (14)		3.35	1 (4)	6 (18)	10 (20)		1.56
2	20 (80)	32 (90)	15 (30)	4 (4)	2.96	4 (16)	10 (30)	10 (20)	3 (3)	2.56
3	14 (56)	33 (99)	22 (44)	2 (2)	2.83	1 (11)	14 (42)	10 (20)	2 (2)	2.52
Total					3.05					2.21
Creativity										
1	33 (132)	27 (81)	11 (22)		3.31	8 (32)	12 (36)	5 (10)	2 (2)	2.96
2	26 (104)	30 (90)	10 (20)	5 (5)	1.63	5 (20)	15 (45)	7 (14)		2.93

3	33 (132)	25 (75)	8 (16)	5 (5)	3.21	9 (36)	11 (33)	7 (14)		3.07
Total					2.72					2.99
Keen Observer										
1	35 (140)	29 (87)	5 (10)	2 (2)	3.37	8 (32)	11 (33)	4 (8)	4 (4)	2.85
2	31 (124)	34 (102)	4 (8)	2 (2)	3.32	5 (20)	13 (39)	7 (14)	2 (2)	2.78
3	21 (84)	36 (108)	13 (26)	1 (1)	3.08	4 (16)	15 (45)	7 (14)	1 (1)	2.81
Total					3.26					2.81
Risk-taking										
1	24 (96)	27 (81)	13 (26)	5 (5)	2.93	9 (36)	13 (39)	3 (6)	2 (2)	3.07
2	14 (56)	32 (96)	17 (34)	8 (8)	2.73	4 (16)	12 (36)	10 (20)	1 (1)	2.70
3	29 (116)	32 (96)	7 (14)	3 (3)	3.23	5 (20)	12 (36)	7 (14)	3 (3)	2.70
Total					2.96					2.82
Objectivity										
1	16 (64)	32 (96)	17 (34)	6 (6)	2.82	6 (24)	9 (27)	12 (24)		2.78
2	17 (68)	37 (111)	16 (32)	1 (1)	2.99	2 (8)	17 (51)	8 (16)		2.78
3	10 (40)	28 (84)	27 (54)	6 (6)	2.59	6 (24)	8 (24)	12 (24)	1 (1)	2.70
Total					2.8					2.75
Critical Thinking										
1	11 (44)	22 (96)	19 (38)	19 (19)	2.35	4 (16)	8 (24)	9 (18)	6 (6)	2.37
2	10 (40)	31 (93)	17 (34)	13 (13)	2.54	1 (4)	9 (27)	9 (18)	8 (8)	2.11
3	11 (44)	31 (93)	19 (38)	10 (10)	2.61	4 (16)	10 (30)	10 (20)	3 (3)	2.56
Total					2.5					2.35
Persistence										
1	19 (76)	36 (108)	14 (28)	2 (2)	3.01	3 (12)	16 (48)	6 (12)	2 (2)	2.74
2	44 (176)	19 (57)	7 (14)	1 (1)	3.49	10 (40)	9 (27)	7 (14)	1 (1)	3.04
3	44 (176)	22 (66)	5 (10)		3.55	8 (32)	16 (48)	3 (6)		3.19
Total					3.35					2.99

Common scientific attitude of grade-7 learners under the special programs when grouped according to types of special program

	H-High	Mo- Moderate	L-Low	P-Poor						
	Special Science Class (n=28)					Special Performing in the Arts (n=70)				
Scientific Attitudes	H (4)	Mo (3)	L (2)	P (1)	Mean	H (4)	Mo (3)	L (2)	P (1)	Me an
Curiosity										
1	12 (48)	16 (48)			3.43	14 (56)	42 (126)	13 (26)	1 (1)	2.99
2	8 (32)	19 (57)	1 (2)		3.25	19 (76)	41 (123)	9 (27)	1 (1)	3.24
3	1 (4)	15 (45)	9 (18)	3 (3)	2.5	9 (36)	38 (114)	16 (48)	7 (7)	2.93
Total					3.06					3.05
Open-mindedness										
1	7 (28)	14 (42)	6 (12)	1 (1)	2.96	16 (64)	42 (126)	11 (22)	1 (1)	3.04
2	11 (44)	15 (45)	1 (2)	1 (1)	3.29	19 (76)	33 (99)	17 (34)	1 (1)	3
3	8 (32)	10 (30)	4 (8)	6 (6)	2.71	7 (28)	19 (57)	25 (50)	19 (19)	2.2
Total					2.99					2.75
Skepticism										
1	8 (32)	13 (39)	6 (12)	1 (1)	3	18 (72)	32 (96)	11 (22)	9 (9)	2.84
2	10 (40)	12 (36)	4 (8)	2 (2)	3.07	14 (56)	32 (96)	18 (36)	6 (6)	2.77
3	5 (20)	9 (27)	9 (18)	5 (5)	2.5	6 (24)	30 (90)	25 (50)	9 (9)	2.47
Total					2.86					2.69
Intellectual Honesty										
1	11 (44)	13 (39)	4 (8)		3.25	22 (88)	35 (105)	13 (26)		3.13
2	12 (48)	8 (24)	7 (14)	1 (1)	3.11	12 (48)	34 (102)	18 (36)	6 (6)	2.74
3	5 (20)	15 (45)	7 (14)	1 (1)	2.86	10 (40)	32 (96)	25 (50)	3 (3)	2.7
Total					3.07					2.86
Creativity										
1	14 (56)	9 (27)	5 (10)		3.32	27 (108)	30 (90)	11 (22)	2 (2)	3.17
2	7 (28)	17 (51)	2 (4)	2 (2)	3.11	24 (96)	30 (90)	13 (26)	3 (3)	3.07
3	15 (60)	9 (27)	2 (4)	2 (2)	2.86	27 (108)	27 (81)	13 (26)	3 (3)	3.11
Total					3.23					3.12
Keen Observer										

1	13 (52)	13 (39)	2 (4)		3.32	30 (120)	27 (81)	7 (14)	6 (6)	3.16
2	12 (48)	14 (42)	2 (4)		3.04	24 (96)	33 (99)	9 (18)	4 (4)	3.1
3	8 (32)	14 (42)	4 (8)	2 (2)	3.32	17 (68)	37 (111)	16 (32)		3.01
Total					3.25					3.12
Risk-taking										
1	11 (44)	14 (42)	2 (4)	1 (1)	3.39	24 (96)	26 (78)	14 (28)	6 (6)	2.97
2	3 (12)	16 (48)	8 (16)	1 (1)	3.36	15 (60)	28 (84)	19 (38)	8 (8)	2.71
3	12 (48)	9 (27)	6 (12)	1 (1)	3	22 (88)	35 (105)	8 (16)	5 (5)	3.06
Total					3.05					3.09
Objectivity										
1	10 (40)	11 (33)	6 (12)	1 (1)	3.07	12 (48)	30 (90)	23 (46)	5 (5)	2.7
2	6 (24)	18 (54)	3 (6)	1 (1)	2.75	13 (52)	36 (108)	21 (42)		2.89
3	4 (16)	14 (42)	7 (14)	3 (3)	3.14	12 (48)	22 (66)	32 (64)	4 (4)	2.6
Total					2.99					2.91
Critical Thinking										
1	5 (20)	8 (24)	8 (16)	7 (7)	3.07	10 (40)	22 (66)	20 (40)	18 (18)	2.34
2	4 (16)	16 (48)	5 (10)	3 (3)	3.04	7 (28)	24 (72)	21 (42)	18 (18)	2.29
3	6 (24)	10 (30)	8 (16)	4 (4)	2.64	9 (36)	31 (93)	21 (42)	9 (9)	2.57
Total					2.59					2.73
Persistence										
1	12 (48)	11 (33)	4 (8)	1 (1)	3.21	10 (40)	4 (12)	16 (32)	3 (3)	1.24
2	16 (64)	10 (30)	2 (4)		3.5	38 (152)	18 (54)	12 (24)	2 (2)	3.31
3	16 (64)	9 (27)	3 (6)		3.46	36 (144)	29 (87)	5 (10)		3.44
Total					3.39					2.66

APPENDIX D

Time Plan

Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Remarks
1. Working Title and Research Problem	November 21, 2019	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
2. Making of Background of the Study, Theoretical Framework, Conceptual Framework, and Paradigm of the Study	November 26-29, 2019	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
3. Checking of Hypothesis, Objectives of the Study, Scope and Limitations, and Operational Definition of Terms	December 3, 2019	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
4. Submission of Review of Related Literature	December 12, 2019	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
5. Completion of Chapter I	December 6, 2019	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
6. Checking of Methodology Introduction, Research Design, Population and Locale of the Study, Research Instruments, and Data Gathering Procedure	January 6, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
7. Making of Treatment of Data	January 13, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
8. Submission of Chapter II	January 15, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
9. Data Gathering	January 20-24, 2020	Researchers, Respondents, and Teachers	Accomplished
10. Analysis and Interpretation of Data	January 27-31, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
11. Discussion of the Results and Interpreted Data	February 4-7, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
12. Checking of Findings, Conclusions,	February 12, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished

Recommendations, and Abstract			
13. Checking of Preliminary Pages	February 14, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
14. Literature Cited	February 19, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
15. Forms and Style	February 20, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
16. 4 Copies of the Whole Books	February 21, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished
17. Final copy of Research paper	March 23, 2020	Researchers and Research Adviser	Accomplished

BIODATA

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Last Name		First Name		Middle Name	
Bay-an		Brandel		Longbas	
Birthdate	November 21, 2001	Nationality	Filipino		
Birth Place	Bot-oan, Catlubong, Buguias, Benguet	Permanent Address	Bot-oan, Catlubong, Buguias, Benguet		
Sex	Male	Blood Type	O		
Civil Status	Single	Height (m)	1.68		
Phone Number	09121311397	Weight (in kilos)	63		

II. FAMILY BACKGROUND

FATHER		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Bay-an	Brandino	Colinio
MOTHER (MAIDEN NAME)		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Longbas	Delfina	Bantasan

III. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Level	School	Academic Awards	Year Graduated
Kindergarten	Amlimay Elementary School	None	2007
Elementary	Bot-oan Elementary School	None	2014
Junior High School	Catlubong National High School	With Honor	2018
Senior High School	Loo National High School	N/A	N/A
Project Course in College		Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation	

IV. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Talents and Hobbies	Memberships in Organizations
Playing Basketball	DRRM
Additional Awards	Life Ambition
N/A	N/A
Motto in Life	
“We may encounter many defeats but we must not be defeated”	

BIODATA

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Last Name	First Name	Middle Name	
Codman	Wenzer	Bonggik	
Birthdate	December 11, 2000	Nationality	Filipino
Birth Place	Loo, Buguias, Benguet	Permanent Address	Loo, Buguias, Benguet
Sex	Male	Blood Type	AB
Civil Status	Single	Height (m)	1.61
Phone Number	09503230925	Weight (in kilos)	62

II. FAMILY BACKGROUND

FATHER		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Codman	Weber	Calixto
MOTHER (MAIDEN NAME)		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Bonggik	Alma	Dangpa

III. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Level	School	Academic Awards	Year Graduated
Kindergarten	Loo Elementary School	With Awards	2007
Elementary	Loo Elementary School	With Honor	2014
Junior High School	Loo National High School	With Honor	2018
Senior High School	Loo National High School	N/A	N/A
Project Course in College		Criminology	

IV. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Talents and Hobbies	Memberships in Organizations
Playing guitar and watching	Music Club and DRRM
Additional Awards	Life Ambition
N/A	N/A
Motto in Life	
"It matters not what someone is born but what they grow to be"	

BIODATA

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Last Name		First Name		Middle Name	
Culop		Dominijoyz		Ablayan	
Birthdate	April 7, 2002	Nationality	Filipino		
Birth Place	Am-am, Tadian, Mountain Province	Permanent Address	Cada-anan, Tadian, Mountain Province		
Sex	Female	Blood Type	O		
Civil Status	Single	Height (m)	1.52		
Phone Number	09506604597	Weight (in kilos)	45 kg		

II. FAMILY BACKGROUND

FATHER		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Culop	Domingo	Bitaga
MOTHER (MAIDEN NAME)		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Ablayan	Alma	Gama

III. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Level	School	Academic Awards	Year Graduated
Kindergarten	Cadad-anan Elementary School	None	2007
Elementary	Cadad-anan Elementary School	With Honor	2014
Junior High School	Loo National High School	With Honor	2018
Senior High School	Loo National High School	N/A	N/A
Project Course in College		Education	

IV. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Talents and Hobbies	Memberships in Organizations
Reading and Watching	Music Club and DRRM
Additional Awards	Life Ambition
N/A	N/A
Motto in Life	
"There will always be an excuse to hinder you from your goal, be stronger than your excuses"	

BIODATA

I. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Last Name		First Name		Middle Name	
Dangpa		Mikeson		Balikid	
Birthdate	April 25, 2001	Nationality	Filipino		
Birth Place	Loo, Buguias, Benguet	Permanent Address	Loo, Buguias, Benguet		
Sex	Male	Blood Type	O		
Civil Status	Single	Height (m)	1.63		
Phone Number	09129002434	Weight (in kilos)	59		

II. FAMILY BACKGROUND

FATHER		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Dangpa	Michael	Oloan
MOTHER (MAIDEN NAME)		
Last Name	First Name	Middle Name
Balikid	Estilita	Ngoyngoy

III. EDUCATIONAL BACKGROUND

Level	School	Academic Awards	Year Graduated
Kindergarten	Loo Elementary School	With Awards	2007
Elementary	Loo Elementary School	With Honor	2014
Junior High School	Loo National High School	With Honor	2018
Senior High School	Loo National High School	N/A	N/A
Project Course in College		Civil Engineering	

IV. ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Talents and Hobbies	Memberships in Organizations
Playing Guitar and Playing Soccer	Football Club, Music Club, Yes-O, and Link Club
Additional Awards	Life Ambition
N/A	N/A
Motto in Life	
“You are a lot better than you probably think you are”	